

Effectiveness of the medicines verification system in Bulgaria: analysis of system connectivity and verification alerts

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Received 24 March 2026 ♦ Accepted 14 April 2026 ♦ Published 7 May 2026

Citation: Milushewa P, Alexandrova J, Paunova I, Todorova A (2026) Effectiveness of the medicines verification system in Bulgaria: analysis of system connectivity and verification alerts. *Pharmacia* 73: e192565. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e192565>

Abstract

Introduction: The medicines verification system was introduced in the European Union to prevent the entry of falsified medicines into the legal supply chain. Bulgaria is an integral part of the European Medicines Verification System (EMVS), maintaining its national repository through the Bulgarian Medicines Verification Organization (BgMVO).

Aim: To evaluate the effectiveness of the medicines verification system in Bulgaria by analyzing the degree of connectivity among end users and the frequency and structure of the generated alerts.

Materials and methods: A documentary analysis was performed using official data from EMVO and BgMVO for 2024. The study focused on connectivity rates, the relative share of verified packs, and the distribution of alerts by type and origin.

Results: By the end of 2024, 99.25% of the mandatory end-user locations in Bulgaria were integrated into the national system. The share of verified packs reached 85.26% in the last quarter of 2024, with an annual average of 82.33%. Generated alerts accounted for 0.062% of all scans, with 73.57% attributed to technical reasons and 26.43% attributed to procedural issues.

Conclusion: Bulgaria demonstrates a high level of technical integration; however, a gap remains between connectivity and the actual frequency of verification and decommissioning. The alert structure shows a predominance of technical factors, suggesting a need for further optimization of software infrastructure and data management processes.

Keywords

Bulgaria, connectivity, falsified medicinal products, medicines verification system, verification alerts

Introduction

According to World Health Organization (WHO) data, approximately one in ten medical products in low- and middle-income countries is estimated to be either substandard or falsified. The therapeutic groups most frequently affected by this issue include anti-infectives (particularly

antibiotics and antimalarials), medicines acting on the central nervous system, analgesics, erectile dysfunction medications, and cytostatics. Falsified medicines pose a significant public health risk, as they lack the required qualitative and quantitative composition and circumvent regulated manufacturing and control procedures. Their

prevalence is observed both in resource-limited settings and in economically developed countries, where factors such as the expansion of online trade, lower costs, and ease of access stimulate unregulated supply chains (World Health Organization 2020). Data from the WHO Global Surveillance and Monitoring System reveal that 21% of reports on falsified medical products between 2013 and 2017 originated from Europe, highlighting the necessity for strengthened regulatory oversight and technological measures to ensure product authenticity (World Health Organization 2017). In response, Directive 2011/62/EU (European Parliament and Council 2011) and Delegated Regulation (EU) 2016/161 (European Commission 2016) established the regulatory framework for the EU-wide medicines verification system. This system mandates the application of safety features—a Unique Identifier (UI) and an Anti-Tampering Device (ATD)—on the outer packaging of prescription medicinal products. Verification and decommissioning occur via a network of national repositories linked to the European Medicines Verification System (EMVS), governed by the European Medicines Verification Organization (EMVO). While marketing authorization holders upload the UIs, wholesalers and pharmacies verify and decommission packs during distribution. Any discrepancy during this process triggers an alert, which is handled according to established protocols (EMVO 2023). As of February 2025, the European Medicines Verification System (EMVS) comprises 30 national repositories covering all countries within the European Economic Area. In Bulgaria, the national medicines verification system is operated by the Bulgarian Medicines Verification Organization (BgMVO), to which wholesalers and pharmacies are connected. When a medicinal product is dispensed to a patient, the pharmacy software performs real-time verification of the unique identifier (UI) against both the national repository and the central European hub. If no discrepancies are detected, the pack is decommissioned; otherwise, an alert is generated. An alert functions as an automated notification triggered by a discrepancy between the scanned UI and the data uploaded to the system by the manufacturer. The frequency and distribution of these alerts serve as key indicators of the system's operational performance and provide insight into the discrepancies encountered in routine clinical practice (Bulgarian Drug Agency 2019; Bulgarian Medicines Verification Organization 2025). The verification process in Bulgaria is further integrated with the digitalization of medicinal product dispensing. Since 1 June 2021, all prescriptions reimbursed by the National Health Insurance Fund (NHIF) have been issued electronically via the National Health Information System (NHIS). As of 1 April 2024, the decommissioning of the unique identifier is a mandatory prerequisite for pharmacy reimbursement for all NHIF-covered medicinal products (Law on Medicinal Products in Human Medicine 2007; National Health Insurance Fund 2024). Subsequent amendments, effective from 1 June 2025, introduced automated real-time verification checks within the NHIS, including the validation of specific verification code pa-

rameters. These measures have established an integrated cross-check mechanism between the NHIS, the NHIF, and the national medicines verification system (National Health Insurance Fund 2025).

In this context, the present study aims to evaluate the functional effectiveness of the medicines verification system by analyzing connectivity rates at both European and national levels and by examining the volume and structure of alerts generated within the EMVS and the BgMVS.

Methods and materials

This study constitutes a retrospective documentary analysis of official statistical data concerning the operation of the medicines verification system at both European and national levels. Aggregated data provided by the BgMVO were utilized, focusing on pharmacy connectivity rates, decommissioning frequencies for the 2024 calendar year, and alerts generated from unsuccessful attempts during the period October–December 2024 in Bulgaria and across the European Union (EU). Furthermore, published summary data from the EMVO were analyzed for all 29 countries connected to the EMVS as of 31 December 2024.

To calculate the indicator relative share of decommissioned packs in relation to all packs dispensed, data from IQVIA on market size (number of packs) were used. According to IQVIA data on market size (number of packs dispensed annually), in 2024 the prescription medicines market across all Member States of the European Union amounted to 10,221,714,185 packs. The size of the Bulgarian market in volume was 159,400,928 packs. The share of the Bulgarian prescription medicines market (in number of packs) was 1.56% of the market in EU countries.

The assessment of connectivity at the European level was conducted based on absolute and relative indicators published by EMVO. Countries were categorized according to their degree of connectivity (full or partial) and the types of participating entities. A comparative analysis was performed to determine Bulgaria's positioning relative to other system participants. Given the aggregated nature of the available data and the comparative objectives of the study, a descriptive analytical approach was considered most appropriate. This approach enables consistent cross-country comparison and facilitates the identification of structural patterns in system performance, including variations in connectivity, decommissioning practices, and alert generation. The use of relative indicators further ensures comparability between countries with differing scales of operation and levels of system implementation.

To contextualize the generated alerts, the study first analyzed the total volume of decommissioned packs and their relative share of all units subject to decommissioning. Based on these relative values, the system's operational effectiveness was assessed in accordance with EMVO criteria. Trends in decommissioning rates for the 2021–2024 period were examined to evaluate the implementation of legislative and technical requirements. The proportion of alerts generated was calculated relative to

the total number of verified packs, with results presented both in aggregate at the European level and by individual member states.

For the scope of this analysis, alerts were categorized into two main groups: technical alerts (A2, A3, A52, and A68) and procedural alerts (A7 and A24). This classification allows for a more precise assessment of the nature of discrepancies. A comparative analysis of the relative share of different alert categories was conducted to identify prevailing trends across different markets. Additionally, alert origins were examined based on the type of entity that triggered them.

A consistent analytical approach was applied to the Bulgarian context. The study presents the relative share of decommissioned packs compared to the total volume of units subject to decommissioning in 2024. Furthermore, the distribution of alerts for the final quarter of 2024 was examined by type and relative proportion relative to the total number of scans. Finally, alert origins were analyzed based on the specific type of entity involved.

Data processing and statistical analysis were conducted using Microsoft Excel. Descriptive statistical methods were applied, including calculations of absolute frequencies, relative proportions, and mean values. The results are presented in tables and figures.

To complement the analysis of alert data, the study also considers the regulatory procedures applied in cases of alert generation. On 2 March 2021, the Bulgarian Drug Agency (BDA) published instructions for managing alerts during verification and decommissioning of medicinal products. At the European level, additional guidelines are used by National Medicines Verification Organizations (NMVOs) and National Competent Authorities (NCAs). When a Bulgarian user generates an alert in the medicines verification system, the Bulgarian Medicines Verification Organization (BgMVO) analyzes the reasons for the alert. When the alert is due to technical reasons (e.g., scanner or software issues) or procedural errors, BgMVO provides guidance to the system user to prevent recurrence. When the analysis indicates a potential suspicion of falsification, the BgMVO prepares a report for the Bulgarian Drug Agency (BDA), which conducts further investigation. In such cases, pharmacies are required to quarantine the medicinal product and provide it to the competent authority.

Limitations of the study

This study has several limitations. Alert data for Bulgaria are restricted to the final quarter of 2024, which may not fully capture annual variability. There is also potential heterogeneity in reporting practices, including differences in national implementation, data reporting standards, and alert classification, which may affect cross-country comparability. In addition, the descriptive nature of the analysis does not allow the establishment of causal relationships between regulatory measures, technical factors, and observed outcomes. Finally, the indicators used (connectivity, decommissioning rate, and alert rate) represent

indirect measures of system performance and may not fully reflect real-world effectiveness in detecting falsified medicinal products.

Despite these limitations, the study provides a structured comparative assessment of the medicines verification system, offering valuable insights into its operational performance and highlighting areas for further optimization and improvement.

Results

Connectivity to the medicines verification system

European level

By the end of 2024, the EMVS had reached near-total coverage, with 99.40% of all entities subject to connectivity successfully integrated. Pharmacies represented the largest relative share (90.16% of all entities), followed by healthcare institutions (5.82%) and wholesalers (3.18%) (Table 1). Full connectivity (100%) was reported in 23 of 29 countries. In the remaining six countries, integration levels exceeded 98%, except for Liechtenstein, where connectivity stood at 17.57%, primarily due to the low integration rate of self-dispensing doctors (Fig. 1). These data indicate a high level of technical readiness of the system at the European level, establishing the prerequisites for its effective operation; however, this does not necessarily guarantee its full functional implementation in practice.

Table 1. Connectivity of entities subject to mandatory integration into the European Medicines Verification System (EMVS), 2024.

Entity type	Connected	Not connected	Total entities
Pharmacies	114,599 (90.13%)	32 (0.03%)	114,631 (90.16%)
Healthcare institutions	6,817 (5.36%)	587 (0.46%)	7,404 (5.82%)
Wholesalers	4,037 (3.18%)	1 (0.001%)	4,038 (3.18%)
Self-dispensing doctors	816 (0.64%)	59 (0.05%)	875 (0.69%)
Other channels	106 (0.08%)	60 (0.05%)	166 (0.13%)
Total by connectivity	126,375 (99.40%)	739 (0.58%)	127,114

Bulgaria

By the end of 2024, 3,317 of 3,342 operational entities in Bulgaria (99.25%) had been connected to the medicines verification system, including 2,952 of the 2,976 community pharmacies (99.19%). The entities that remain unconnected are predominantly pharmacies operating under a seasonal regime (Table 2).

According to the analysis of the EMVO, Bulgaria is classified among the countries demonstrating high, although not yet complete, system connectivity, placing it within the upper range of European performance indicators for this measure.

Figure 1. Relative connectivity of entities by country.

Table 2. Connectivity of entities subject to mandatory connection to the Bulgarian Medicines Verification System (BgMVS) in Bulgaria as of the end of 2024.

Entity type	Connected	Not connected	Total entities
Pharmacies	2,952 (88.33%)	24 (0.72%)	2,976 (89.05%)
Healthcare institutions	204 (6.10%)	1 (0.03%)	205 (6.13%)
Wholesalers	161 (4.82%)	0 (0.00%)	161 (4.82%)
Total by connectivity	3,317 (99.25%)	25 (0.75%)	3,342

Decommissioning rates and alert generation

European level

The relative share of decommissioned packs in relation to all packs dispensed on prescription increased from 75.6% at the beginning of 2021 to 92.4% by the end of 2024, with the 90% threshold exceeded for the first time during the final quarter of 2024 (Fig. 2).

Classification of verification alerts

The verification system categorizes alerts into several primary groups based on their nature and regulatory significance. The first group includes UI-element mismatches, such as unknown serial numbers (A3), unknown batch numbers (A2), expiry date mismatches (A52), or batch number mismatches (A68). These alerts are most frequently associated with technical issues, including data upload or encoding errors, scanning difficulties, or software integration discrepancies. The second group comprises status-related alerts, such as attempts to dispense or process a pack that has already been decommissioned (A7, A24). These are classified as procedural alerts, reflecting a conflict between the current transaction and the

pack status recorded in the repository. Additionally, alert A32 (duplicate serial number), while potentially resulting from technical errors during bulk operations or repeated scans, remains critical as it may indicate the presence of multiple packs bearing an identical UI.

During the last quarter of 2024, a total of 2,966,234 alerts were recorded in the EMVS, representing 0.08% of all scans performed. A downward trend in the relative share of alerts is observed, with the proportion remaining below 0.1% during most months of 2024. Regarding their structure, 36.97% of alerts are technical (A2, A3, A52, A68), while 63.03% are procedural (A7, A24) (Fig. 3). In ten countries, the alert rate exceeds the target threshold of 0.05% established by EMVO.

Approximately 85% of all alerts originate from five countries—France, Netherlands, Germany, Spain, and Portugal—suggesting a concentration of issues in larger pharmaceutical markets. In most countries, alerts are generated predominantly at the level of community pharmacies (Fig. 4).

Bulgaria

During the last quarter of 2024, a total of 55,285,919 scans were performed in Bulgaria, representing 85.26% of all dispensing events subject to decommissioning. The overall annual share of decommissioned packs reached 82.33%, placing the country 21st among the 27 analyzed countries. A positive trend was observed throughout 2024, with the relative share of decommissioning operations increasing from 80.21% to 85.26% (Fig. 5).

According to data for the last quarter of 2024, a total of 34,288 alerts were generated in the BgMVS, representing 0.062% of all scans performed in Bulgaria. Of these alerts, an average of 82% originated from community pharmacies, 10.33% from marketing authorization holders and parallel traders, and 7.66% from wholesalers and other stakeholders (Fig. 6). This places Bulgaria ninth in terms

EMVS Overview - Decommission Rate

Figure 2. Relative share of performed decommissioning operations in relation to all dispensing events subject to decommissioning in Europe.

Figure 3. Relative distribution of alert types generated in the European Medicines Verification System (EMVS).

of the number of alerts generated among the countries included in the analysis.

Regarding the types of alerts recorded during the last quarter of 2024, a total of 1,972 alerts corresponded to alert code A2 (5.75% of all generated alerts), 13,803 to A3 (40.26%), 78 to A52 (0.23%), 9,371 to A68 (27.33%), and 9,064 to A7 and A24 (26.43%) (Fig. 7).

These data indicate that 25,224 alerts (73.57%) were attributable to technical causes, while 9,064 alerts (26.43%) resulted from procedural causes.

The alert rate in Bulgaria is relatively low (approximately 0.05–0.06% of all transactions). More than 90% of alerts are due to technical reasons. The remaining cases, mainly related to breaches of the legal supply chain, are treated as suspected falsification and are reported to the Bulgarian Drug Agency. However, publicly available data on confirmed falsified cases are not reported.

Discussion

Connectivity to the medicines verification system

The results indicate that by the end of 2024, the European medicines verification system had achieved near-complete coverage of entities subject to connection. Nevertheless, in-

complete integration persists in certain countries, suggesting that specific national characteristics affect implementation. Data further indicate that the absence of full connectivity cannot be attributed to a single universal factor. In France, incomplete connectivity is likely associated with a longer transitional period for system adaptation, whereas in Portugal and Austria—despite formally achieving full connectivity—other challenges are reported, including lower verification and decommissioning rates or a predominance of technical alerts.

These findings suggest that connectivity levels alone are insufficient indicators of system effectiveness; they should instead be interpreted within the context of actual operational use. This observation aligns with the well-documented discrepancy between technological availability and practical utilization in real-world settings, particularly within the EMVS framework (Naughton et al. 2016).

A particularly illustrative example is Liechtenstein, where low connectivity is largely attributable to limited participation by dispensing physicians. One possible explanation is the national system's dependence on the Swiss regulatory framework, coupled with the absence of a legal obligation to implement Directive 2011/62/EU requirements in Switzerland. Similar regulatory disparities have been identified as factors influencing the effectiveness of international traceability systems (Wickett et al. 2024). Bulgaria reports near-complete connectivity, with the remaining unconnected entities consisting predominantly of seasonal pharmacies. This indicates a high level of technical readiness at the national level. However, as demonstrated by subsequent data, high connectivity does not automatically guarantee effective operational utilization.

Frequency of verification, decommissioning, and regulatory preconditions

The observed variability in verification and decommissioning frequencies across countries indicates that technical integration and actual system use are not equivalent indicators. A similar relationship between regulatory design, technological infrastructure, and real-world utilization has been highlighted in analyses of digital pharmaceutical traceability (Sarkar 2022). Nine countries, including Bulgaria, remain below the 90% target threshold. In the Bulgarian context, a discrepancy exists between near-complete entity connectivity and lower decommissioning frequencies.

Figure 4. Number and types of alerts generated by country.

Decommission for dispense in relation to the Market Size

Figure 5. Relative share of decommissioning operations in relation to all dispensing events subject to decommissioning in Bulgaria.

An analysis of the national regulatory framework reveals two distinct dispensing regimes: medicinal products reimbursed by the NHIF and those dispensed outside this mechanism. For NHIF-reimbursed prescriptions, UI

decommissioning is functionally mandatory, as it is integrated into electronic reporting and the generation of a national dispensing registration number. The software architecture precludes transaction completion without suc-

Alert Distribution

Figure 6. Relative share of alerts generated in Bulgaria by place of origin.

Figure 7. Relative share of alerts recorded in the BgMVS during Q4 2024.

successful EMVS decommissioning—an example of effective alignment between regulatory and technical requirements. Conversely, for non-reimbursed products, no equivalent technical restriction exists, allowing transactions to be finalized without verification. This regulatory imbalance likely explains the lower overall decommissioning rate, suggesting the issue stems from regulatory enforcement rather than technical limitations. The positive trend in 2024, following new NHIF requirements, supports the hypothesis that integrated regulatory–technical mechanisms significantly impact system implementation.

Distribution of system alerts and technical maturity

The alert structure reveals substantial differences between Bulgaria and European averages. While procedural alerts predominate at the European level, technical alerts dominate in Bulgaria. This may indicate varying levels of technical maturity or differences in reporting and classification methodologies. This interpretation should be considered with caution, as the predominance of technical alerts may also be influenced by differences in national reporting prac-

tices, system configuration, and the level of end-user training. Similar observations have been reported in the literature, where technical discrepancies are often associated with data upload inconsistencies, software interoperability issues, and scanning errors rather than actual product-related risks (Naughton et al. 2016; Wickett et al. 2024). Therefore, while the observed alert structure provides useful insights into system performance, further studies based on disaggregated data would be necessary to more precisely determine the underlying causes. Frequent technical difficulties—such as software integration issues, barcode scanner misconfiguration, and data exchange errors—likely influence the perceived operational burden and the quality of pharmaceutical counseling. In this context, technical alerts should be viewed not as systemic malfunctions but as indicators for interface optimization and end-user training. The fact that a similar profile exists in other regional markets suggests that regulatory implementation, software standardization, and unified training influence alert distribution.

The Bulgarian Drug Agency does not have an obligation or established practice to publicly disclose the outcomes of investigations into suspected falsified medicines; however, the legal framework foresees administrative sanctions upon confirmed violations.

It should be emphasized that the European Medicines Verification System has a predominantly preventive function, significantly reducing the risk of falsified medicines entering the legal supply chain.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that the Bulgarian medicines verification system has achieved high technical readiness and near-complete connectivity. While Bulgaria ranks among the highest in formal connectivity within the EMVS, decommissioning frequencies reveal a significant gap between connectivity and practical use. Decommissioning rates remain below target, confirming that connectivity is an insufficient metric for effectiveness. Results suggest that utilization is largely driven by regulatory mechanisms, particularly the integration of BgMVS, NHIF, and NHIS. The Bulgarian model illustrates that aligning regulatory and technical requirements enhances real-world implementation.

Technical alerts predominate in Bulgaria, highlighting challenges in software solutions and equipment, con-

trusting with European trends where procedural alerts are more common. Ultimately, system effectiveness in Bulgaria must be evaluated through a comprehensive analysis of practical implementation rather than technical integration alone. Achieving full operational effectiveness will require further refinement of the regulatory framework and optimization of technical infrastructure to reduce inconsistencies and ensure consistent decommissioning practices.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

Funding

The study was financed with funds from the state budget, provided through the Ministry of Education and Science (MES) to the Science Fund at the Medical University–Varna for financing the scientific activity inherent in state higher education institutions under project No. 22018.

Author contributions

All authors contributed equally to the conception and design of the study. Data collection and analysis were performed by I.P., A.T and J.A. The first draft of the manuscript was written by P.M, and all authors critically revised the manuscript for important intellectual content. All authors have read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.